

GAM-NICHE TOOL

FACT SHEET #11

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) under the ecological niche theory

DESCRIPTION

GAM-NICHE is a new open access tool developed by AZTI (Valle et al. 2023) to build Species Distribution Models (SDMs) under the ecological niche theory (Citores et al. 2020). It provides a GitHub tutorial in R language with an application to marine species. A tutorial provides guidance on how to use shape-constrained generalized additive models (SC-GAMs) to build SDMs under the ecological niche theory framework, based on the development and application to marine fish by Citores et al. (2020).

While a variety of statistical methods have been developed for species distribution modelling, a general problem with most of these habitat modelling approaches is that the estimated response curves can display biologically implausible shapes which do not respect ecological niche theory. This is because species response curves are fit statistically with any assumption or restriction, which sometimes do not respect the ecological niche theory. To better understand species response to environmental changes, GAM-NICHE considers theoretical background such as the ecological niche theory and pursuing the unimodality of the response curve with respect to environmental gradients.

Picture source: <https://gam-niche.azti.es/>

The GAM-NICHE model represents a significant advance in the science of marine ecology. Developed by AZTI's Global Change of Marine Ecosystems team, this model uses advanced statistical techniques known as shape constrained generalised additive modelling (SC-GAM) to predict the distribution of marine species. What makes GAM-NICHE special is its ability to incorporate ecological niche theory, which asserts that each species has a range of environmental conditions in which it can survive and thrive. By applying shape constraints to GAMs, the model avoids predictions that are not biologically plausible and aligns more closely with what we know about species ecology.

A study, applying the GAM-NICHE model to study 3D distribution of marine species, focused on the 30 most important species for commercial fishing in the Atlantic: Using the GAM-NICHE model as a basis, the AZTI research team has gone a step further and developed 3D species distribution models, i.e. incorporating the vertical dimension of the ocean. The development of these three-dimensional models of the habitat of the main commercial fish species in the Atlantic, which account for 67% of the total biomass catch, provides an improved spatial representation of the probability of occurrence of these species.

FACTS AT A GLANCE

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KEYWORDS

Species Distribution Models (SDM),
Ecological Niche Theory (ENT),
Ecological Niche Models (ENM),
shape constrained generalised
additive modelling (SC-GAM)

LINKS TO RELATED PROJECTS

MISSION ATLANTIC Tools
<https://missionatlantic.eu/tools/>

LINKS TO RELATED WORK

GAM-NICHE web site:
<https://gam-niche.azti.es/>

REFERENCE

Valle, M et al (2024) "Pan-Atlantic 3D distribution model incorporating water column for commercial fish" *Ecological Modelling*, vol. 490, n. 110632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2024.110632..>

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL

TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment

Understanding the distribution of species allows fishermen and marine resource managers to plan their activities more effectively. This not only helps to ensure that fishing practices are sustainable, but also minimises the impact on marine ecosystems. In addition, the GAM-NICHE model can be a valuable tool for predicting how climate change may alter the distribution of these species in the future, which is vital for adapting conservation and fishing strategies.

BACKGROUND

As described on the GAM-NICHE Website by AZTI (<https://gam-niche.azti.es/>), Species Distribution Models (SDMs) are numerical tools that combine observations of species occurrence or abundance at known locations with information on the environmental and/or spatial characteristics of those locations. SDMs are widely used as a tool for understanding species spatial ecology and are also known as ecological niche models (ENM) or habitat suitability models. According to ecological niche theory, species response curves are unimodal with respect to environmental gradients (Hutchinson 1957).

APPLICATION

The application of the GAM-NICHE model in marine research offers a new understanding of ocean ecology. By providing a sound basis for sustainable management of marine resources, this model promises to be a useful tool for ensuring a sustainable future for commercial fisheries. With climate change and ocean acidification presenting unprecedented challenges, tools such as GAM-NICHE are essential to adapt our practices in the future.

This holistic approach not only benefits the fishing industry, but also plays a crucial role in protecting marine biodiversity and addressing the effects of climate change. By better understanding where and how fish live, informed decision-making is enabled, balancing economic needs with the urgent need to conserve our oceans for future generations.

Potential Applications include:

- Estimation of species distribution, recruitment, spawning, cartography
- Determining main factors affecting a species
- Monitoring and trend analysis
- Restoration (identification of suitable areas)
- Shifts in biodiversity
- Climate change studies (projections, impacts, vulnerability, adaptation)
- Conservation: definition of areas to protect
- Assessment of anthropogenic pressures
- Identification of (un)exploited areas

RELATION TO MISSION 'RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS': GAM-NICHE may contribute to all three Mission Objectives (MO). However specifically, the EU Biodiversity Strategy '30 (MO1) and the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy (MO3). GAM-NICHE also contributes to the Mission enabler Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System, known as Digital Twin of the Ocean.